

Biodiversity Meets Data (BMD) – Consent Form

Please initial each box

If you are happy to participate in the project, please initial each box as appropriate (leave blank any box for which you prefer not to give consent) and then sign this form at the end. Please read the information (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16948244>) sheet before deciding whether to participate in the project.

1.	I have read the information sheet (found here) and have been given the opportunity to ask further questions.	
2.	I understand that participating in the project involves in-person and/or online activities such as events, workshops, focus groups, discussion forums, interviews and questionnaires. I understand that I am not obligated to participate in all/any project activities, but may participate in the activities that are most relevant, interesting and accessible to me (e.g. for in person activities I may attend the activities that are closest to me geographically).	
3.	I have read the privacy statement (found here) and understand how my data will be stored and used during and after the end of the project.	
4.	I understand that my words may be quoted in outputs such as academic publications, articles, books, reports, and web sites related to the research project and that my personal details will be anonymised in any project outputs (i.e. my name, occupation, organisational affiliation will be assigned a generic descriptor). I understand I can ask for specific quotes or statements not to be used (or to be redacted from the data) if I wish.	
5.	I understand that the project team may be taking photographs/videos during events and activities (e.g. workshops and demonstrations) and I give my consent for these photographs/videos to be reproduced for educational and/or non-commercial purposes, in educational materials, publications, advertising and promotional materials, social media platforms, websites and press releases.	

Co-funded by
the European Union

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
**State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI**

Swiss Confederation

6.	I understand that some project activities (e.g. interviews, focus groups) may be audio/visually recorded in full for the purpose of supplementing notetaking and/or the creation of transcripts for analysis by project researchers to inform the development and publication of project outputs. For activities that are being recorded, the project team will inform me of this.	
7.	There are two alternative options for the use of your data. Please choose one of the following two options:	
	<p style="text-align: center;">OR</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I agree for the data I provide to be retained by the research team in secure storage for the requirements of funders. This means that the data will be accessible to the research team only. 	
8.	I agree that members of the project team can re-contact me at a future date should they wish to follow up on this research.	
9.	<p>I understand that my taking part is voluntary; I can withdraw from the project later, and I do not have to give any reasons for why I no longer want to take part (<i>and this will be without any impact on any related services I am using</i>). I understand the implications of withdrawing at different points during the life of the project, and understand that it may not be possible to withdraw my data following anonymisation, publication of outputs or if my data is part of a group activity.</p> <p>I understand that if I want to withdraw from the project, I can contact Tami Wooldridge (twooldridge@rbge.org.uk) who will discuss with me how existing data will be managed, as outlined in the Participant Information Sheet.</p>	
10.	I agree to take part in the Biodiversity Meets Data (BMD) project.	

Name of participant

Date

Signature

Name of researcher

Date

Signature
